

Metadata description for archival material

Title: Archival material from the Schomburg Center, New York Public Library

Description: Archival material from the Schomburg Center (New York Public Library). The material contains personal correspondence and investigations directed by Gunnar Myrdal, Professor of Economics, during this period in New York working on what later became the book “An American Dilemma”, funded by the Carnegie Corporation of New York.

The Schomburg Center, New York Public Library, 515 Malcolm X Blvd, New York, NY 10037, USA.

Microfilm. Correspondence and studies on African American minority in the United States and their living conditions and legal rights.

Some photographed

Date of data collection: 29.5.-2.6.2024 and 4.6.2024-5.6.2024

Keywords: Gunnar Myrdal, The American Dilemma, Critical Race Theory, Anti-Discrimination

Author: Karolina Stenlund, The Centre of Excellence in Law, Identity and the European Narratives (EuroStorie)

Publications on the material: Work in progress

Preservation of research data: The material will be stored in Zenodo.